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TECHNOLOGY****SCHOOL HEADS' TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP BEHAVIOURS ON
TEACHERS' WORKING PATTERNS IN THE DIVISION OF BILIRAN****Sherly C. Enage, Susan S. Bantor, FRANCISCO M. EBIO, JR*****DOI:****ABSTRACT**

The study generally aimed to determine the level of school heads' transformational leadership behaviours on teachers' working patterns in the Division of Biliran. Using the descriptive-survey research design, it included 126 secondary school teachers as respondents. The secondary school heads demonstrated high level of transformational leadership behaviours in providing vision or inspiration, modelling, fostering commitment to group goals, providing individual support, providing intellectual stimulation and holding high performance expectations. On the other hand, the secondary school teachers possessed high level of working patterns in terms of organizational commitment, organizational citizenship behaviour and teaching job satisfaction. School heads' demonstrations of transformational leadership behaviours have significant correlations to teachers' working patterns. A follow-up research maybe conducted on designing a comprehensive qualitative study that includes an interview component with students, parents, stakeholders and local government unit representatives to explore greater depth the relationships and interactions between perceived school heads' leadership behaviours and teachers' working patterns.

KEYWORDS: school heads; transformational leadership behaviours; teachers; working patterns.

INTRODUCTION

Transformational leadership has been characterized as superior leadership performance that occurs when leaders broaden, elevate the interests of their employees, generate awareness and acceptance of the purposes or mission of the group, and stir their employees to look beyond their own self-interest for the good of the group. This leadership stimulates and inspires followers to achieve beyond expectation and in the process developing their own capacities (Bass, 2000).

The success of the organization depends not only on how the organization exploits its human capital and competencies but also on how it stimulates commitment to the organization (Nguni, 2006). The committed employees who are highly motivated to contribute their time and energy to the pursuit of organizational goals are increasingly acknowledged to be the primary asset available to an organization.

Today's decentralization reforms are geared towards school restructuring, teachers' organizational commitment, job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behaviour (Bogler, 2002). Gaining understanding of the way transformational leadership behaviour influences these three teachers' work behaviour and motivational aspect, is likely to enhance the prospect of school improvement.

In the Division of Biliran, reforms also need to be implemented due to the demands of the changing time, especially with the birth of the K to 12 Program. The reform initiative no doubt requires significant capacity development on the part of school administrators and teachers as well as stakeholders.

It is along this premise that this study has been conducted to determine the level of school heads' transformational leadership behaviours on teachers' working patterns in the Division of Biliran in terms of organizational commitment, organizational citizenship behaviour and teachers' job satisfaction. Thus, results will shed great insights into the significant roles of administrators and teachers in carrying out quality education.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study generally aimed to find out the school heads' level of transformational leadership behaviours on teachers' working patterns in the secondary schools in the Division of Biliran.

Specifically, it sought to:

Determine the level of transformational leadership behaviours of secondary school heads in terms of:

- 1.1 providing vision or inspiration;
- 1.2 modelling;
- 1.3 fostering commitment to group goals;
- 1.4 providing individual support;
- 1.5 providing intellectual stimulation; and
- 1.6 holding high performance expectations.

Find out the level of teachers' working patterns in terms of:

- 1.7 organizational commitment;
- 1.8 organizational citizenship behaviour; and
- 1.9 job satisfaction.

Ascertain the significant relationship between the transformational leadership behaviours of school heads and working patterns of teachers.

Null Hypothesis

HO₁: There is no significant relationship between transformational leadership behaviours of school heads and working patterns of teachers.

Framework of the Study

This study took hold of the following theoretical and conceptual frameworks as its main and solid foundations in the due course of its proceedings.

Theoretical framework. This study is premised on James McGregor Burns (1978) first idea of transformational leadership. According to Burns, transforming leadership is a process in which "leaders and followers help each other to advance to a higher level of morale and motivation".

The transforming approach creates significant change in the life of people and organizations. It redesigns perceptions and values and changes expectations and aspirations of employees. Transforming leaders are idealized in the sense that they are a moral exemplar of working towards the benefit of the team, organization and/or community. Burns theorized that transforming and transactional leadership was mutually exclusive styles.

In support, Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory proposes that people are motivated by multiple needs in hierarchical order. Lower-order needs must be fulfilled before higher-order needs are satisfied.

The theories suggest that to improve job attitudes and productivity, administrators must recognize and attend to both sets of characteristics and not assume that an increase in satisfaction leads to decrease in unpleasurable dissatisfaction. Job characteristics related to what an individual does – that is, to the nature of the work he performs – apparently have the capacity to gratify such needs as achievement, competency, status, personal worth and self-realization, thus making him happy and satisfied.

Conceptual framework. This study anchored on the transformational leadership behaviours of the secondary school heads in the Division of Biliran. To deeply appraise the intention of the study, it also looked into the working patterns of teachers in terms of organizational commitment, organizational citizenship behaviour and job satisfaction.

Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework of the study

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The following literature is reviewed to provide substance and support to the study.

Griffith (2004) stated that transformational leadership makes subordinates or followers aware of the importance of their jobs and performance to the well-being of the organization as well as their own needs for personal career advancement and growth and able to motivate subordinates to work harder for the good of the organization. It is the leadership that raises the level of motivation of the followers through leaders' connection and engagement process (Northouse, 2010).

Robbins, et. al. (2010) stressed that transformational leadership stimulates and inspires or transforms subordinates to strive hard in order to achieve extraordinary outcomes. Draft (2010) added that it is a leadership that inspires followers to believe in their own potential so as to create a better prospect and future for the organization as well as to believe in the leader personally. It is the leadership that involves exercising influence on the attitudes and assumptions of organization members and building commitment for the organization's mission, objectives and strategies (Dessler & Starke, 2004).

Bass & Riggio (2006) asserted that transformational leadership focuses more on change, and inspires followers to commit to a shared vision and goals for an organization or unit, challenging them to be innovative problem solvers, and developing followers' leadership capacity via coaching, mentoring and provision of both challenge and support.

Transformational leadership is associated with subordinate's moral values (Mulla & Krishnan, 2011). The positive effect of transformational leadership is that it enhances self- knowledge thus, increasing the performance expectation value to the financial performance of the teams (Somech & Wenderow, 2006).

Leaders in any organization are expected to carry out tasks with limited resources to the maximum level in order to maintain the competitive edge and to sustain profitability position of the organization (Riaz & Haider, 2010). Leadership is the major element in order to preserve and improve an organization's competitive advantage over its competitor.

Transformational leadership provides a flexible approach to change which allows a leader's personal style and the context to vary (Leithwood & Jantzi, 2006). Flexibility allows organizations to solve problems while raising followers' commitment, motivation, empowerment and elevating the leader and the follower to a higher purpose to support institutional change.

The ability to raise follower commitment is essential for a transformational leader to accomplish change, especially in uncertain times. Commitment creates greater individual productivity on behalf of the organization. Greater productivity allows the organization to meet its goals (Hay, 2006).

Voon, et. al. (2011) showed the stronger relationship between transformational leadership and job satisfaction. Organization has to enhance job satisfaction among its workers to increase commitment. Said leadership is a key factor of high job satisfaction thus increasing employee performance.

Raelin (2011) revealed that employees in public sector organization have greater degree of organizational commitment in comparison to private sector organizations and also the job satisfaction increases or decreases based on increase or decrease in organizational commitment. Organizational commitment is proven as the catalyst for enhancing job satisfaction level of employee.

Scotter (2002) suggested that while a single act of organizational citizenship behaviour is not likely to earn anyone a pay raise or promotion, over time and situations, employees' organizational citizenship behaviour should influence supervisors' decisions about their contributions to the organizations and potential for advancement. He added that employees who are more helpful, cooperative, term-oriented are more likely to be judged effective employees. They are more likely to receive positive supervisory feedback concerning their chances of advancing to the next level of the organization and more likely to be encouraged to remain in the organization.

The foregoing review of literature is significantly related and served as strong foundation in conceptualizing this study.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study was limited in terms of the mode of data gathering which was through the use of survey questionnaires. It covered only 17 secondary schools of the Division of Biliran. It focused on the impact of school heads' transformational leadership behaviours in terms of providing vision or inspiration, modelling, fostering commitment to group goals, providing individual support, providing intellectual stimulation, holding high performance expectation on teachers' working patterns in terms of organizational commitment, organizational citizenship behaviour and teachers' job satisfaction in the Division of Biliran. The respondents were limited to the selected secondary school teachers.

METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the methods used in the study. It describes and discusses the research design, research locale, research subjects, research instrument, data gathering procedure, data scoring and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

This study used the descriptive survey as it considered appropriate for a questionnaire being utilized as a tool for gathering data. The researcher personally administered the questionnaire to the teacher-respondents in order to gather accurate, valid and reliable data.

The variables considered for analysis were the level of transformational leadership behaviours of secondary school principals in terms of: *providing vision or inspiration, modelling, fostering commitment to group goals, providing individual support, providing intellectual stimulation and holding high performance expectation*. On the other hand,

it also considered for analysis the level of working patterns in terms of: *organizational commitment, organizational citizenship behaviour* and *job satisfaction* of selected secondary school teachers in Biliran Division.

Research Locale

This study covered the 17 public secondary schools in the Division of Biliran. The schools involved were: Biliran National Agricultural High School, Naval School of Fisheries, Naval National High School, Almeria National High School, Tabunan National High School, Kawayan National High School, Tucdao National High School, Bool National High School, Culaba National Vocational School, Manlabang National High School, Cabucgayan National School of Arts and Trades, Cabucgayan National High School, Maripipi National Vocational School, Viga National High School, Hingatangan National High School, Naval Night High School and Lucsoon National High School.

Research Subjects

The study focused on the 17 secondary schools in the Division of Biliran. One hundred twenty six (126) teachers were tapped as respondents. They were selected teachers in the said division. One (1) teacher per learning area was chosen to comprise eight (8) teachers from the seven (7) secondary schools and seven (7) teachers from secondary schools with small number of teachers. Random sampling through fish bowl method was done in order to determine the respondent from each learning area.

Research Instrument

The survey instrument for this research was developed from a combination of four separate instruments designed by different researchers in school leadership, organizational commitment, organizational citizenship behaviours and job satisfaction.

Part I elicited the level of transformational leadership behaviours of the school head as perceived by teacher respondents. The questionnaire used a five-point Likert-type scale to be attached to each indicator. Respondents were asked to state the level of transformational leadership behaviour with each statement regarding their school head. The instrument identified six aspects of transformational leadership behaviour: providing vision or inspiration, modelling, fostering commitment to group goals, providing individual support, providing intellectual stimulation and holding high performance expectation.

Part II elicited the teacher respondents' organizational commitment. It was patterned from the instrument developed by Mowday, Steers and Porter (1982). It dealt specifically with measuring the level of organizational commitment among individual employees. The instrument used a five-point Likert Scale to assess employees' level of commitment to their current position.

Part III covered the teacher respondents' organizational citizenship behaviour developed by Smith et. al. (1983). It used a five-point Likert Scale.

Part IV highlighted the teacher respondents' job satisfaction which was patterned from the teacher satisfaction survey developed by Evans and Johnson (1996).

Data Gathering Procedure

Permission was asked from the Schools Division Superintendent before the questionnaires were distributed to the respondents. Further instructions and clarifications were made during the distribution of said questionnaires. After retrieval, careful tallying, scoring, interpretation and analysis of the data gathered were made.

Data Scoring

The level of school heads' transformational leadership behaviour and teachers' working patterns were scored using a Likert-type scale from 1 to 5. The mean range, weight and qualitative description are as follow:

Mean Range	Weight	Qualitative Description
4.51 – 5.00	5	Very High
3.51 – 4.50	4	High
2.51 – 3.50	3	Moderate
1.51 – 2.50	2	Low
1.0 – 1.50	1	Very Low

Statistical Treatment of the Data

Descriptive statistics such as mean, range, percentage and frequency counts were used to describe the results and findings. Appropriate statistical tool was utilized to compute the data in order to come up with valid analysis.

Chi-square was used to test the relationship between school heads' transformational leadership behaviours and teachers' working patterns.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This portion of the study presents the results and discussion of the survey conducted to the 126 secondary school teachers in the Division of Biliran. Said results were organized and presented with respect to the research objectives covering the level of school heads' transformational leadership behaviours as perceived by the teachers and its relationship to teachers' working patterns in terms of organizational commitment, organizational citizenship behaviour and job satisfaction.

Level of Transformational Leadership Behaviours of School Heads

This section discusses the respondents' perceptions on the level of school heads' transformational leadership behaviours in terms of *providing vision or inspiration, modelling, fostering commitment to group goals, providing individual support, providing intellectual stimulation, and holding high performance expectation.*

Level of Transformational Leadership Behaviours of School Heads in Terms of *Providing Vision or Inspiration.*

Table 1 presents the level of transformational leadership behaviours of school heads in terms of *providing vision or inspiration.*

The data on the table showed that all indicators of the school heads' level of transformational leadership behaviours in terms of providing vision or inspiration were rated high. Item *excites staff of visions of what may be accomplished when they work together* had the highest weighted mean of 3.84, followed by *gives teachers sense of overall purpose, has both the capacity and judgment to overcome obstacles, commands respect from everyone in school and makes teachers feel and act like leaders* with respective weighted means of 3.78, 3.71, 3.67 and 3.63.

The average weighted mean of 3.73 revealed that the school heads' level of transformational leadership behaviours in terms of *providing vision or inspiration* was rated high. This would imply that teachers are motivated to work considering that they were guided and inspired by their school head.

Table 1

Level of Transformational Leadership Behaviours of School Heads in Terms of Providing Vision or Inspiration

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
has both the capacity and judgment to overcome obstacles	3.71	High
excites staff with visions of what may be accomplished when they work together	3.84	High
commands respect from everyone in school	3.67	High
makes teachers feel and act like leaders	3.63	High
gives teachers sense of overall purpose	3.78	High
Average Weighted Mean	3.73	High

Level of Transformational Leadership Behaviours of School Heads in Terms of Modelling. Table 2 presents the level of transformational leadership behaviours of school heads in terms of modelling.

It can be gleaned from the data that all indicators of the school heads' transformational leadership behaviours in terms of modelling were rated high by the respondents. Item *symbolizes success and accomplishment within teachers' profession* got the highest weighted mean of 3.79, followed by *leads by doing rather than by simply telling*, 3.74 and *provides good models for teachers to follow*, 3.69.

Table 2
Level of Transformational Leadership Behaviours of School Heads in Terms of Modelling

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
leads by doing rather than by simply telling	3.74	High
symbolizes success and accomplishment within teachers' profession	3.79	High
Provides good models for teachers to follow	3.69	High
Average Weighted Mean	3.74	High

The average weighted mean of 3.74 revealed that school heads' level of transformational leadership behaviours in terms of *modelling* was rated high. Results would imply that teachers tend to follow and emulate their school head considering that the latter showed good image to the former both as a leader and a doer.

Level of Transformational Leadership Behaviours of School Heads in Terms of Fostering Commitment to Group Goals. Table 3 presents the level of transformational leadership behaviours of school heads in terms of *fostering commitment to group goals*.

Table 3
Level of Transformational Leadership Behaviours of School Heads in Terms of Fostering Commitment to Group Goals

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
provides for teachers' participation in the process of developing school goals	3.86	High
encourages teachers to work towards the same goal	3.86	High
uses problem solving with staff members to generate school goals	3.62	High
works towards whole staff consensus in establishing priorities for school goals	3.64	High
encourages teachers regularly to evaluate progress towards achievement of school goals	3.76	High
Average Weighted Mean	3.75	High

Data disclosed that all indicators of school heads' level of transformational leadership behaviours in terms of *fostering commitment to group goals* were rated high by the respondents. Items *provides for teachers' participation in the process of developing school goals* and *encourages teachers to work towards the same goal* had both the highest weighted mean of 3.86. These were followed by items *encourages teachers regularly to evaluate progress towards achievement of school goals*, *works towards whole staff consensus in establishing priorities for school goals* and *uses problem-solving with teachers to generate school goals* with weighted means of 3.76, 3.64 and 3.62 respectively.

The average weighted mean of 3.75 showed that the level of transformational leadership behaviours of school heads in terms of fostering commitment to group goals was rated high. This would imply that the leadership being portrayed by the school heads tends teachers to be more dedicated and loyal to their jobs.

Level of Transformational Leadership Behaviours of School Heads in Terms of Providing Individual Support. Table 4 shows the level of transformational leadership behaviours of school heads in terms of *providing individual support*.

Table 4
Level of Transformational Leadership Behaviours of School Heads in Terms of Providing Individual Support

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
provides for extended training to develop teacher's knowledge and skills	3.69	High
provides necessary resources to support teacher in doing job properly	3.51	High
treats teacher as an individual with unique needs and expertise	3.77	High
takes teacher's opinion into consideration	3.69	High
behaves in a manner thoughtful of teacher's personal needs	3.71	High
Average Weighted Mean	3.67	High

Data disclosed that all indicators of school heads' level of transformational leadership behaviours in terms of *providing individual support* were rated high by the respondents. Item *treats teacher as an individual with unique needs and expertise* had the highest weighted mean of 3.77. This was followed by item *behaves in a manner thoughtful of teacher's personal needs* (3.71), items *provides for extended training to develop teacher's knowledge and skills* and *takes teacher's opinion into consideration* equally got a weighted mean of 3.69, and item *provides necessary resources to support teacher in doing job properly*, 3.51.

The average weighted mean of 3.67 revealed that the level of transformational leadership behaviours of school heads in terms of *providing individual support* was perceived high by the respondents. This would imply that the leadership manifested by the school head likely transforms the teacher, as an individual, to perform more in his/her job.

Level of Transformational Leadership Behaviours of School Heads in Terms of Providing Intellectual Stimulation. Table 5 presents the level of transformational leadership behaviours of school heads in terms of *providing intellectual stimulation*.

Table 5
Level of Transformational Leadership Behaviours of School Heads in Terms of Providing Intellectual Stimulation

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
challenges teacher to examine some basic assumptions he/she has about work	3.71	High
stimulates teacher to think about what he/she is doing for students	3.88	High
provides information that helps teacher think of ways to improve	3.79	High
Average Weighted Mean	3.79	High

Data disclosed that all indicators of school heads' level of transformational leadership behaviours in terms of *providing intellectual stimulation* were rated high by the respondents. Item *stimulates teacher to think about what he/she is doing for students* got the highest mean of 3.88. Items *provides information that helps teacher think of ways to improve* and *challenges teacher to examine some basic assumptions he/she has about work* got the respective weighted means of 3.79 and 3.71.

The average weighted mean of 3.79 revealed that the level of transformational leadership behaviours of school heads in terms of providing intellectual stimulation was considered high. This implies that the leadership portrayed by the school heads would likely transform teachers to be highly intellectual thus delivering better service to their students.

Level of Transformational Leadership Behaviours of School Heads in Terms of *Holding High Performance Expectations*. Table 6 shows the level of transformational leadership behaviours of school heads in terms of *holding high performance expectations*.

Table 6
Level of Transformational Leadership Behaviours of School Heads in Terms of Holding High Performance Expectations

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
insists only on the best performance from teachers	3.68	High
shows teachers that there are high expectations from them as professionals	3.87	High
will not settle for second best in performance from teachers' work	3.56	High
Average Weighted Mean	3.70	High

It can be gleaned from the data that all indicators of school heads' level of transformational leadership behaviours in terms of *holding high performance expectations* were rated high by the respondents.

Item *shows teachers that there are high expectations from them as professionals* got the highest weighted mean of 3.68, *insists only on the best performance from teachers* had 3.68 and *will not settle for second best in performance from teachers' work*, 3.56.

The average weighted mean of 3.70 revealed that the level of school heads' transformational leadership behaviours in terms of *holding high performance expectations* was perceived high. This would imply that teachers tend to give their best performance in every assigned task thus turning students to achieve better.

Summary of School Heads' Level of Transformational Leadership Behaviours. Table 7 shows the summary of school heads' level of transformational leadership behaviours.

Table 7
Summary of School Heads' Level of Transformational Leadership Behaviours

Transformational Leadership Behaviour	Average Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
providing vision or inspiration	3.73	High
modelling	3.73	High
fostering commitment to group goals	3.75	High
providing individual support	3.67	High
providing intellectual stimulation	3.79	High
holding high performance expectations	3.70	High
Overall Mean	3.73	High

Data on Table 7 revealed that all behaviours portrayed by school heads with respect to their transformational leadership were rated high by the respondents.

The highest average weighted mean of 3.79 was marked by *providing intellectual stimulation*, followed by *fostering commitment to group goals* (3.75), *providing vision or inspiration* and *modelling* both marked equal average weighted mean (3.73), *holding high performance expectations* (3.70) and *providing individual support* (3.67).

The overall mean of 3.73 disclosed that the school heads' level of transformational leadership behaviours was perceived high. This would imply that quality management of school heads yields better performance for both teachers and students in the Division of Biliran.

Level of Teachers' Working Patterns

This section discusses the level of teachers' working patterns in terms of *organizational commitment*, *organizational citizenship behaviour* and *job satisfaction*.

Level of Teachers' Working Patterns in Terms of Organizational Commitment. Table 8 presents the level of teachers' working patterns in terms of *organizational commitment*.

Table 8 Level of Teachers' Working Patterns in Terms of Organizational Commitment

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
teacher feels like part of the organization	4.20	High
much of life would be disrupted if teacher leaves the organization	3.60	High
organization has a great deal of personal meaning for the teacher	4.10	High
even if it were advantageous, teacher feels it would not be right to leave the organization	3.93	High
trust is violated if teacher quits job	3.79	High
teacher feels guilty if he/she leaves the organization	3.79	High
teacher would not leave organization because he/she has obligation to the people	4.15	High
Average Weighted Mean	3.94	High

Data revealed that all indicators of the teachers' level of working patterns in terms of *organizational commitment* were rated high by the respondents.

Item *teacher feels like part of the organization* got the highest weighted mean of 4.20. This was followed by *teacher would not leave organization because he/she has obligation to the people* (4.15), *organization has a great deal of personal meaning for the teacher* (4.10), *even if it were advantageous, teacher feels it would not be right to leave the organization* (3.93), *trust is violated if teacher quits job* and *teacher feels guilty if he/she leaves the organization* both got equal mean (3.79) and *much of life would be disrupted if teacher leaves the organization* (3.60).

The average weighted mean of 3.94 showed that teachers' level of working patterns in terms of *organizational commitment* was perceived high. This implied that teachers would likely perform well in their job.

Level of Teachers' Working Patterns in Terms of Organizational Citizenship Behaviour. Table 9 presents the level of teachers' working patterns in terms of *organizational citizenship behaviour*.

It can be gleaned from the data that all indicators of teachers' level of working patterns in terms of *organizational citizenship behaviours* were rated high by the respondents.

The highest weighted mean of 4.21 was marked by indicator *volunteers to do other school-related duties*, followed by *teacher does not unnecessarily go out of school compound during working hours* (4.18), *evaluates accomplishment at the end of day's work* (4.17), *informs school head of scheduled absence* (4.09), *volunteers to orient and guide new teachers* (3.97), *suggests innovation for school improvement* (3.87), *helps teachers having heavy workload*

Table 9 Level of Teachers' Working Patterns in Terms of Organizational Citizenship Behaviour

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
willing to teach classes of absent teachers	3.78	High
willing to do non-teaching duties of absent teachers	3.68	High
volunteers to do other school-related duties	4.21	High
volunteers to orient and guide new teachers	3.97	High
helps teachers having heavy workload	3.81	High
evaluates accomplishment at the end of day's work	4.17	High
informs school head of scheduled absence	4.09	High
teacher does not unnecessarily go out of school compound during working hours	4.18	High
assists school heads' work	3.43	High
suggests innovation for school improvement	3.87	High
Average Weighted Mean	3.92	High

(3.81), willing to teach classes of absent teachers (3.78), willing to do non-teaching duties of absent teachers (3.68) and assists school head's work (3.43).

The average weighted mean of 3.92 revealed that teachers' level of working patterns in terms of *organizational citizenship behaviours* was considered high. Result implied that teachers' cooperation, coordination and collaboration with colleagues and school head would likely contribute to school performance and effective school management.

Level of Teachers' Working Patterns in Terms of Job Satisfaction. Table 10 shows the level of teachers' working patterns in terms of *job satisfaction*.

Table 10 Level of Teachers' Working Patterns in Terms of Job Satisfaction

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
teaching job gets recognition from the community	3.90	High
teaching job is a secured employment	4.40	High
teaching job gives help to people	4.51	Very High
teaching job compensates salary received	3.48	High
teaching job provides chance for promotion	3.79	High
teaching job gives feeling of success	4.25	High
Average Weighted Mean	4.05	High

Data showed that indicator *teaching job gives help to people* got the highest mean of 4.51 and perceived very high. All other indicators were rated high, namely: *teaching job is a secured employment* (4.40), *teaching job gives feeling of success* (4.25), *teaching job gets recognition from the community* (3.90), *teaching job provides chance for promotion* (3.79) and *teaching job compensates salary received* (3.48).

The average weighted mean of 4.05 revealed that the level of teachers' working patterns in terms of *job satisfaction* was high. This implied that the teachers' feeling of being secured, contented and rewarded in their job would likely contribute to better school performance.

Summary of Teachers' Level of Working Patterns. Table 11 presents the summary of teachers' level of working patterns.

Table 11 Summary of Teachers' Level of Working Patterns

Working Patterns	Average Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
organizational commitment	3.94	High
organizational citizenship behaviour	3.92	High
job satisfaction	4.05	High
Overall Mean	3.97	High

Data revealed that teachers' working patterns in terms of *organizational commitment*, *organizational citizenship behaviour* and *job satisfaction* were all rated high with the average weighted means of 3.94, 3.92 and 4.05 respectively.

The overall mean of 3.97 revealed that the level of teachers' working patterns was considered high. This implied that the commitment, behaviour and satisfaction portrayed by teachers would likely result to better scholastic performance of students.

Relationship Between School Heads' Transformational Leadership Behaviours and Teachers' Working Patterns in Terms of Organizational Commitment. Table 12 presents the relationship between school heads' transformational leadership behaviours and teachers' working patterns in terms of *organizational commitment*.

Table 12 Relationship Between School Heads' Transformational Leadership Behaviours and Teachers' Working Patterns in Terms of Organizational Commitment

Variables	r	Computed t	Table value	Decision
providing vision or inspiration	0.28	3.25	1.98	HO ₂ rejected
modelling	0.31	3.63		
fostering commitment to group goals	0.31	3.63		
providing individual support	0.30	3.50		
providing intellectual stimulation	0.28	3.25		
holding high performance expectation	0.33	3.89		

Alpha = .05 (two-tailed)

Data revealed that - the null hypothesis that there was no significant relationship between transformational leadership behaviours of school heads and working patterns of teachers was rejected. The fact that there was a significant relationship between the two groups, result would imply that the higher sense of transformational leadership behaviours displayed by school heads, the higher also teachers would show commitment in their job.

Relationship Between School Heads' Transformational Leadership Behaviours and Teachers' Working Patterns in Terms of Organizational Citizenship Behaviour. Table 13 presents the relationship between school heads' transformational leadership behaviours and teachers' working patterns in terms of organizational citizenship behaviour.

Table 13 Relationship Between School Heads' Transformational Leadership Behaviours and Teachers' Working Patterns in Terms of Organizational Citizenship Behaviour

variables	r	Computed t	Table value	Decision
providing vision or inspiration	0.28	3.25	1.98	HO ₁ rejected
modelling	0.29	3.38		
fostering commitment to group goals	0.28	3.25		
providing individual support	0.30	4.04		
providing intellectual stimulation	0.30	3.49		
holding high performance expectation	0.43	5.30		

Alpha = .05 (two-tailed)

Data revealed that – the null hypothesis that there was no significant relationship between school heads' transformational leadership behaviours and teachers' working patterns was rejected. Since there was a significant relationship between the two groups, data would imply that the higher level of transformational leadership behaviours manifested by the school head, the more teachers would reflect desirable behaviours toward their job.

Relationship Between School Heads' Transformational Leadership Behaviours and Teachers' Working Patterns in Terms of Job Satisfaction. Table 14 presents the relationship between school heads' transformational leadership behaviours and teachers' working patterns in terms of job satisfaction.

Table 14 Relationship Between School Heads Transformational Leadership Behaviours and Teachers' Working Patterns in Terms of Job Satisfaction

variables	r	Computed t	Table value	Decision
providing vision or inspiration	0.45	5.61	1.98	HO ₁ rejected
modelling	0.44	5.46		
fostering commitment to group goals	0.50	6.38		
providing individual support	0.43	5.30		
providing intellectual stimulation	0.40	4.86		
holding high performance expectation	0.42	5.15		

Alpha = .05 (two-tailed)

Data showed that – the null hypothesis that there was no significant relationship between school heads' transformational leader behaviours and teachers' working patterns was rejected. Considering that there was a significant relationship between the two groups, data would imply that the higher level of transformational leadership behaviours is manifested by the school head, the more satisfied are the teachers with respect to their job.

CONCLUSIONS

The secondary school heads in the Division of Biliran, Philippines displayed high level of transformational leadership behaviours in terms of: *providing vision or inspiration, modelling, fostering commitment to group goals, providing individual support, providing intellectual stimulation and holding high performance expectations.*

On the other hand, secondary school teachers possessed high level of working patterns in terms of: *organizational commitment, organizational citizenship behaviour and job satisfaction.*

The school heads' manifestation of transformational leadership behaviours influenced the teachers' working patterns.

RECOMMENDATIONS

There is a strong need to reinforce the value of *transformational leadership behaviours* as an effective means of achieving quality leadership.

The secondary school teachers may formulate innovations and other effective strategies to sustain and enhance the level of their positive outlook on their working patterns in terms of *organizational commitment, organizational citizenship behaviour and job satisfaction*.

The school leaders need to be instilled the awareness of the power that these transformational leadership behaviours hold. Behaviours outlined in this study could be useful as self-evaluation instruments for them to gain a sense of their own access and ability.

Institutionalization and sustainability of effective transformational leadership behaviours may be properly implemented in schools to reach the goal of improving the quality of an organization and excellence in education in the Division of Biliran, Philippines.

Lastly, a follow-up study may be conducted by designing a comprehensive qualitative study that includes an interview component with students, parents, local government unit representatives and other stakeholders to explore in greater depth the relationships and interactions between perceived administrative behaviour, organizational commitment, organizational citizenship behaviour, job satisfaction and other variables.

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APPENDIX
SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear Colleague,

Please feel free to answer this questionnaire. Data derived would be used for the study entitled: School Heads' Transformational Leadership Behaviours on Teachers' Working Patterns in Biliran, Philippines. Rest assured all your responses will be kept confidential.

Thank you.

Sincerely,
The Researcher

I. Personal Profile

Name (optional): _____
Age: _____ Sex: _____ Civil Status: _____
Highest Educational Attainment: _____
Number of Years in Teaching: _____
Number of Years in Teaching in Present Station: _____

II. School Heads' Transformational Leadership Behaviours

(Please encircle only the number)

Providing Vision or Inspiration	VL	L	M	H	VH
Has both the capacity and judgment to overcome obstacles	1	2	3	4	5
Excites staff with visions of what may be accomplished when they work together	1	2	3	4	5
Commands respect from everyone in school	1	2	3	4	5
Makes teachers feel and act like leaders	1	2	3	4	5
Gives teachers sense of overall purpose					
Modelling					
Leads by doing rather than by simply telling	1	2	3	4	5
Symbolizes success and accomplishment within teachers' profession	1	2	3	4	5
Provides good models for teachers to follow	1	2	3	4	5
Fostering Commitment to Group Goals					
Provides for teachers' participation in the process of developing school goals	1	2	3	4	5
Uses problem solving with staff members to generate school goals	1	2	3	4	5
Works towards whole staff consensus in establishing priorities for school goals	1	2	3	4	5
Encourages teachers regularly to evaluate progress towards achievement of school goals	1	2	3	4	5
Providing Individual Support					
Provides for extended training to develop teachers' knowledge and skills	1	2	3	4	5
Provides necessary resources to support teacher in doing job properly	1	2	3	4	5
Treats teacher as an individual with unique needs and expertise	1	2	3	4	5
Takes teachers' opinion into consideration	1	2	3	4	5
Behaves in a manner thoughtful of teachers' personal needs	1	2	3	4	5
Providing Intellectual Stimulation					
Challenges teacher to examine some basic assumptions he/she has about work	1	2	3	4	5
Stimulates teacher to think about what he/she is doing for students	1	2	3	4	5
Provides information that helps teacher think of ways to improve	1	2	3	4	5

Holding High Performance Expectations					
Insists only on the best performance from teachers	1	2	3	4	5
Shows teachers that there are high expectations from them as professionals	1	2	3	4	5
Will not settle for second best in performance from teachers' work	1	2	3	4	5

III. Teachers' Working Patterns

Organizational Commitment	VL	L	M	H	VH
Teacher feels like part of the organization	1	2	3	4	5
Much of life would be disrupted if teacher leaves the organization	1	2	3	4	5
Organization has a great deal of personal meaning for the teacher	1	2	3	4	5
Even if it were disadvantageous, teacher feels it would not be right to leave the organization	1	2	3	4	5
Trust is violated if teacher quits job	1	2	3	4	5
Teacher feels guilty if he/she leaves the organization	1	2	3	4	5
Teacher would not leave organization because he/she has obligation to the people	1	2	3	4	5
Organizational Citizenship Behaviour					
Willing to teach classes of absent teachers	1	2	3	4	5
Willing to do non-teaching duties of absent teachers	1	2	3	4	5
Volunteers to do other school-related duties	1	2	3	4	5
Volunteers to orient and guide new teachers	1	2	3	4	5
Helps teachers having heavy workload	1	2	3	4	5
Evaluates accomplishment at the end of day's work	1	2	3	4	5
Informs school head of scheduled absence	1	2	3	4	5
Teacher does not unnecessarily go out of school compound during working hours	1	2	3	4	5
Assists school head's work	1	2	3	4	5
Suggests innovation for school improvement	1	2	3	4	5
Job Satisfaction					
Teaching job gets recognition from the community	1	2	3	4	5
Teaching job is a secured employment	1	2	3	4	5
Teaching job gives help to people	1	2	3	4	5
Teaching job compensates salary received	1	2	3	4	5

Legend:

- VL - Very Low
- L - Low
- M - Moderate
- H - High
- VH - Very High